

RELIGIOSITY AS A FUNCTION OF ADJUSTMENT AMONG URBAN MALE COLLEGE STUDENTS

Samiullah Ansari

Assistant Professor

Department of Psychology, Government Degree College, Bagaha (W. Champaran)

ABSTRACT

The aims of the present study were to explore the effects of religiosity on adjustment among urban college Male students. The sample consists of 100 male students reading in Muzaffarpur town. Bihar. The data were collected from collected from 100 students with the help of Mohsin-Shamsad Adaptation (Hindi) of “Bell’s Adjustment Inventory” and L. I. Bhushan’s Religiosity Scale. The objective of the study was to examine the relationship between the social status with those of home health, social and emotional adjustment. The results reveal that orthodox Hindu student groups significantly high adjustment low religiosity than that of orthodox Muslim students group on different dimension of adjustment like-home, social and emotional except health adjustment.

Keywords: Religiosity, Adjustment, Urban male college Students, Orthodox

INTRODUCTION

The term adjustment refers to the process by which a living organism maintains a balance between its needs and the circumstances that influence the satisfaction of these needs. Adjustment is one of the most important psychological activities of human beings. If anyone wants satisfaction in life, they have to adjust themselves with their environment. Adjustment is precarious and even changing balance between need and desires of the individual on the one hand demands of the environment or society on the other. Adjustment may be defined as a process of altering behaviour to reach a harmonious relationship with the environment. When people say they are in an “adjustment period” they typically mean that they are going through a process of change and are searching for some level of balance or acceptance with the environment, others, or themselves. Each and every situation of life demands that the person concerned should be able to effectively perform in accordance with some guiding principles and should be able to strike a balance among various forces. Coleman (1956) is of the view that “the effectiveness of the individuals effort to his need and adapt to his environment” is called adjustment.

Many studies have also investigated the influence of religious involvement on academic achievement in college. One study found that attendance at religious services and religious

Observation increases the hours students spend studying and in extracurricular activities as well as increases their academic achievement and decreases hours spent partying (Mooney 2010). Another study reiterated the point of religion providing an alternative social scene (Dalessandro 2016). The relation between the social connectedness in religion and academics was of significance in one study, reporting that, “social integration and peer connections were the primary predictors of academic resiliency,” (Ekwonye and DeLauer 2019). Students in some research took note of the supposed impact of their spirituality, with students who did well in their academics crediting their spirituality as the cause, and those who did poorly credited their lack of spirituality as the cause (Fukofuka 2007). The impact of spirituality on academic hardships and stressors was examined in depth in one source and was found to be

an excellent resource for managing these aspects of academic and personal life (Ekwonye et al. 2020).

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE ADJUSTMENT PROBLEM

Adjustment refers to a harmonious relationship between the person and his environment through which his needs are satisfied in accordance with social demands. The adjustment process is a universal sequence that can be identified in the behaviour of organism from the lowest species up to man. If individual experiences have so shaped his personality that he is well prepared to play the roles, which are expected of the status assigned to him within a given environment and if his needs are met by playing such roles, then we say that he is well adjusted.

On the other hand, if experience has not preferred him to play the roles of his assigned status if the environment is such that he is denied the normal status for which his experience has prepared him and his fundamental needs are not met, then we say he is maladjusted. Maladjustment is often termed as mental illness or psychopathology frequently considered the number one health problem of our era, which is characterized by pollution, corruption and dissolution of the stable social system.

Adjustment is not only the problem of one society but it is the problem of all societies. Whole society is divided on the basis of culture, region and economic status. If this stage, students especially feel many adjustment problems. Only teachers and educated parents can provide the right type of education and make them aware of the problems of adjustment of adolescence. If the adolescents of a country would be maladjusted then the progress of a country is not possible. So for the proper guidance to the adolescents, proper education is needed. There are high incidents of mild adjustment and maladjustment among the students of adolescent group, therefore this study will provide sufficient material to know the cases of maladjustment of the students of government senior secondary school and this study will definitely help to guide the students of this age group.

REVIEW OF LITRATURE

Various studies have been conducted on adjustment alike factors.

Kumari, R. & Singh, A. P. (2015) examined that the age and locale are significant factors in determining the level of general adjustment of women criminals and interaction of age and locale is not significant in the determination of general adjustment of women criminals.

Kaur, P. (2016) find out the adjustment of secondary school students in relation to spiritual intelligence. The results showed that there exists no significant difference between the adjustment of male and female secondary school students. The results also revealed that there exists a positive relationship between the adjustment and spiritual intelligence of secondary school student's district.

Emmalee Bosma (2024) studied how college students' level of religiosity influences their academic performance, mental health, sense of purpose and identity, and feelings of belonging and connection at the University of South Dakota (USD). The findings of this research suggest each of the four dimensions of the college experiences researched is impacted in at least a small way by religiosity, especially mental health and purpose and identity.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

HYPOTHESIS

Religiosity will prove to be a significantly factor in determining different dimensions of adjustment among male students.

This broad hypothesis was dived into following sub-Hypotheses:

Sub-H1- Orthodox Hindu male students will be significantly higher than orthodox Muslim male students in scoring home adjustment.

Sub-H2- Orthodox Muslim male students will be significantly higher than Orthodox Hindu male students in scoring health adjustment.

Sub-H3 Orthodox Hindu male students will be significantly higher than Orthodox Muslim male students in scoring emotional adjustment.

Sub-H4- Orthodox Hindu male students will be significantly higher than orthodox Muslim male students in scoring social adjustment.

METHODOLOGY

SAMPLE

The present study the incidental-cum-purposive sample was found suitable and appropriate to be used here. For the purpose. Naturally, the present study was conducted on an incidental-cum-purposive sample consisting of 100 (One Hundred) students of studding undergraduate classes of colleges of Muzaffarpur District Head-Quarter. The sample consisted of only the students in the age group of 14 to 20 years. The subjects were matched in respect of same socio-economic status and the like as far as practicable.

TESTS OF THE PRESENT RESEARCH:-

In the present research the following tools were used:

(i) Personal information Schedule

A personal Data Sheet was used to obtain the information's regarding personal and background factors of the participants.

(ii) Mohsin-Shamsad Adaptation (Hindi) of Bell's Adjustment Inventory

Bell Adjustment Inventory contained 140 statements. When translated statements were item analysed, 5 statements were not found appropriate and they were excluded. The final version of Mohsin-Hussain Adjustment Inventory contained only 135 statements. The reliability and Validity of the scale have also been calculated. The scale has also been validated odd/even reliability with Spearman-Brown formula and test- retest technique it is 0.92 and 0.87. High score indicate poor adjustment and lower score indicate better adjustment.

(iii)L. I. Bhushan's Religiosity Scale-

For measuring religiosity level of subjects 'Religiosity Scale' constructed and standardized by Bhushan, L. I (2006) has been used. The scale consists of 36 items. This is five point Likert type scale comprising both positive and negative items. For positive items a score of 5,4,3,2 or 1 is awarded for totally agree, agree, cannot say, disagree and totally disagree responses respectively. The Reliability co-efficient of the scale has been reported be .82 whereas it has content validity and predictive validity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table- 01

Showing Means, S.Ds and t- Ratios of Home Adjustment scores of Orthodox Hindu and Orthodox Muslim students Sub-Group.

Groups	N	M	SD	df	t-value	Level of Significance
Urban Orthodox Muslim Male students	30	41.25	9.68	48	3.16	.01
Urban Orthodox Hindu Male students	20	32.14	12.89			

Table-0.1 shows the mean home adjustment scores of high religiosity subjects in Orthodox Muslim Male students than that of Orthodox Hindu Male student’s group i.e.41.25 and 32.14, respectively (Table- 0.1). The obtained t-ratio is 3.16 which are significant at 0.1. In the lower mean score on the part of Orthodox Hindu Male students group are significantly low religiosity and high adjustment on home than that of Orthodox Muslim Male students group. The result may be discussed in low religiosity group has obtained significantly lower score in orthodox Hindu Male students group and also significantly higher score on Orthodox Muslim students group. So, the hypothesis that the Orthodox Hindu male students group will be significantly higher than the orthodox Musim male students group on home adjustment towards the dimension of adjustment stands fully verified.

Table-02

Showing Means, S.Ds and t- Ratios of Health Adjustment scores of Orthodox Hindu and Orthodox Muslim students Sub-Group.

Groups	N	M	SD	df	t-value	Level of Significance
Urban Orthodox Muslim Male students	30	33.04	11.71	48	2.36	.01
Urban Orthodox Hindu Male students	20	40.60	10.12			

Table-0.1 shows the mean health adjustment scores of high religiosity subjects in Orthodox urban Hindu Male students than that of Orthodox urban Muslim Male student’s group i.e. 33.04 and 40.60, respectively (Table- 0.2). The obtained t-ratio is 2.36 which are significant at 0.1. In the lower mean score on the part of Orthodox Muslim male students group are significantly low religiosity and high adjustment on health than that of Orthodox Hindu male students group. The result may be discussed in low religiosity group has obtained significantly lower score in orthodox Muslim male students group and also significantly higher score on Orthodox Hindu students group. So, the hypothesis that the orthodox Muslim Male students group will be significantly higher than the orthodox Hindu Male students group on health adjustment towards the dimension of adjustment stands fully verified.

Table-03

Showing Means, S.Ds and t- Ratios of Social Adjustment scores of Orthodox Hindu and Orthodox Muslim students Sub-Group.

Groups	N	M	SD	df	t-value	Level of Significance
Urban Orthodox Muslim Male students	30	42.12	9.96	48	3.04	.01
Urban Orthodox Hindu Male students	20	32.37	11.62			

Table-0.3 shows the mean social adjustment scores of high religiosity subjects in Orthodox urban Hindu Male students than that of Orthodox urban Muslim male student's group i.e.42.12 and 39.80, respectively (Table- 0.3). The obtained t-ratio is 3.04 which are significant at 0.1. In the lower mean score on the part of Orthodox Hindu male students group are significantly low religiosity and high adjustment on social than that of Orthodox Muslim Male students group. The result may be discussed in low religiosity group has obtained significantly lower score in orthodox Hindu male students group and also significantly higher score in Orthodox Hindu students group. So, the hypothesis that the orthodox Muslim male students group will be significantly higher than the orthodox Hindu male students group on social adjustment towards the dimension of adjustment stands fully verified.

Table-04

Showing Means, S.Ds and t- Ratios of Emotional Adjustment scores of Orthodox Hindu and Orthodox Muslim students Sub-Group.

Groups	N	M	SD	df	t-value	Level of Significance
Urban Orthodox Muslim Male students	30	46.20	10.06	48	3.50	.01
Urban Orthodox Hindu Male students	20	34.52	12.41			

Table-0.4 shows the mean emotional adjustment scores of high religiosity subjects in Orthodox urban Hindu Male students than that of Orthodox urban Muslim Male student's group i.e.46.20 and 34.52, respectively (Table- 0.4). The obtained t-ratio is 3.50 which are significant at 0.1. In the lower mean score on the part of Orthodox Hindu male students group are significantly low religiosity and high adjustment on emotion than that of Orthodox Muslim male students group. The result may be discussed in low religiosity group has obtained significantly lower score in orthodox Hindu male students group and also significantly higher score on Orthodox Muslim male students group. So, the hypothesis that the orthodox Hindu male students group will be significantly higher than the orthodox Muslim male students group on emotional adjustment towards the dimension of adjustment stands fully verified.

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